

GENOMED4ALL

D8.2

Training programme definition

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

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GENOMED4ALL Training programme definition

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Abstract

This deliverable comprises the first phase of the design of the GenoMed4All training programme, which is focused on the definition of the topics, methodologies and training materials.

Keywords

Education, training, webinar, educational catalogue, training pills.

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC**CO** Confidential to GenoMed4All project and Commission Services*** Deliverable types:****R:** document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).**DEM:** demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.**DEC:** websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.**OTHER:** software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
B1MG	Beyond 1 Million Genomes
CDSS	Clinical decision support system
CPT	Current Procedural Terminology
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
EHA	European Hematology Association
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
EJP RD	European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases
ePAGs	European Patient Advocacy Groups
ERDRI	European Rare Disease Registry Infrastructure
ERICA	European Rare Disease Research Coordination and Support Action
EU	European Union
EU-RD-Platform	European Union Rare Disease platform
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FL	Federated Learning
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GWAS	Genome-Wide Association Studies
HDs	Hematological diseases
HGNC	HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
HSCT	Hematopoietic Stem Cell Transplant
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
IDs	Stable Identifiers
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LOINC	Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes

MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MIN.	Minimum
ML	Machine Le
MM	Multiple Myeloma
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
NN	Neural Network
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
Orphanet's ORDO	Orphanet Rare Disease ontology
PCORnet	National Patient-Centered Clinical Research Network
PET/CT	Positron Emission Tomography–Computed Tomography
PFS	Progression-Free Survival
RD	Rare Disease
RHD	Rare Hematological Diseases
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
SCDO	Sickle Cell Disease Ontology
SNOMED-CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
SW	Software
VCF file	Variant Call Format File
WBMRI	Whole-Body Magnetic Resonance Imaging
WMHR	White Matter Hyperintense Regions

Executive summary

This deliverable is the result of the collaborative work performed by GenoMed4All Educational Scientific/Technical Committee towards the **definition of the GenoMed4All training programme**.

During the periodic meetings, the pillars of the educational strategy have been defined by:

- ❑ Fixing the objectives of the programme: **increase awareness** and **education/training**.
- ❑ Defining the **5 main topic areas** for the development of the lectures.
- ❑ Establishing the **Webinar courses** as the format for knowledge delivery.
- ❑ Stipulating **different training levels** for the adaptation of the content according to the audience's knowledge.
- ❑ Specifying the **dynamic of the webinar session**.
- ❑ Determining ERN-EuroBloodNet and GenoMed4All websites as the **platform for the management of the webinars and content produced**.

ERN-EuroBloodNet, VHIR & AP-HP, and AUSTRALO will work together for the **Dissemination & Communication** to increase the programme's outreach by utilizing the educational material produced. An **evaluation of the training program** has been also considered.

1 General overview

This deliverable (**D8.2 – GenoMed4All training programme definition**), is presented in the framework of GenoMed4All's **WP8 – Genomics standardization, value-based healthcare, Open Science data and training/education**, specifically within task **T8.4 – Training and education programme**. This document is focused on the design and development of the GenoMed4All training and educational programme towards providing adequate concepts and instructions on the use of the technologies (applied in this project) and clinical outcomes to the Hematological Diseases (HDs) communities including researchers, practitioners, patients or their relatives and other interested stakeholders.

D8.2 represents GenoMed4All's first steps followed for the definition and design of the training program of the project. This deliverable has been structured in three main sections:

- ❑ The **Executive Summary** where the primary points of this document are mentioned.
- ❑ **Section 1** is the **General overview**, where the purpose of the deliverable is outlined.
- ❑ **Section 2** comprises the description of the overall training programme:
 - **Section 2.1** is devoted to the definition of the **GenoMed4All Educational Scientific/Technical Committee (GenoMed4All ES/TC)**
 - **Section 2.2** describes the **Methodology** applied for the development of the training programme.
 - **Section 2.3** includes the five main areas of content that comprise the **Structure of the programme**.
 - **Section 2.4** is concerned with the **Courses and webinars definition**, where the preliminary form of the courses is presented.
 - **Section 2.5** explains the **Communication and Dissemination strategy**, where objectives and tools are described.
 - **Section 2.6** marks out the procedure that will be taken into consideration for the **Evaluation of the program**.
- ❑ **Section 3** outlines the **Conclusions** of the present document.

This document should be regarded as a living document, subject to update as the training programme matures and evolves in the following phases of development. The final programme, together with all material produced and its evaluation results will be described in the report that will be produced at the end of the project (**D8.6 – Final report on the GenoMed4All training**).

2 GenoMed4All training programme

The GenoMed4All training programme has been designed, in line with the ERN-EuroBloodNet webinars programme strategy for educational courses, to **increase awareness** and to **educate & train** on the different topics involved in the GenoMed4All project.

2.1 GenoMed4All Educational Scientific/Technical Committee (GenoMed4All ES/TC)

The spinal cord of this training programme is formed by the five main areas (see [Section 2.3](#)) identified by the **GenoMed4All Educational Scientific/Technical Committee (GenoMed4All ES/TC)** ([Table 1](#)). This committee, established exclusively to develop the GenoMed4All educational module, comprises 17 members from 13 partners, alongside two patients' representatives.

GenoMed4All ES/TC Member	Partner
María del Mar Mañú-Pereira	VHIR & ERN-EuroBloodNet
Maria A. Rodríguez-Sánchez	VHIR & ERN-EuroBloodNet
Diana López	AUS
Mariangela Pellegrini	AP-HP & ERN-EuroBloodNet
Patricia Alonso	UPM
Marilena Bicchieri	ICH
Maria Paola Boaro	UNIPD
Gastone Castellani	UNIBO
Raffaella Colombatti	UNIPD
Matteo Della Porta	ICH
Nathan Lea	I-HD
Marina Martello	UNIBO
Vincent Planat	DEDALUS
Anna Rizzo	DW
Tiziana Sanavia	UNITO
Babita Singh	CRG
Carolina Terragna	UNIBO
Silvia Uribe	UPM
Eduard J van Beers	UMC UTRECHT
Jacqueline Dubow	MDS Alliance (international) & CCM
Sophie Wintrich	MDS UK Patient Support Group & MDS Alliance

Table 1. GenoMed4All Educational Scientific/Technical Committee (GenoMed4All ES/TC)

2.2 Methodology

The action plan established for the definition of the GenoMed4All's training programme relies on the work of the **GenoMed4All ES/TC**. Regular meetings were organized to ensure a 360° overview of the project's topics, the accuracy of the content and to guarantee the excellence of the programme.

As a starting point, the outcomes of the **Patient Engagement e-Workshop**, have been taken into consideration for the definition of the programme (**Figure 1**). The meeting was a joint effort by **GenoMed4All's consortium** and ERN-EuroBloodNet: it gathered 70+ registrants and speakers from the **Thalassemia International Federation**, **Myeloma Patients Europe**, the **MDS Alliance** and **EURORDIS**. All the information about the event description and agenda can be found in the **project website's event archive**. This workshop, hosted by the project in September 2021, has been useful to conduct a landscape analysis of potential topics to be addressed by educational programs related to GenoMed4All's areas of intervention.

In particular, this exercise was designed to evaluate the level of awareness on Artificial Intelligence (AI) of the patients' communities of Myelodysplastic syndromes (MDS), Multiple myeloma (MM) and Sickle Cell disease (SCD). Indeed, the aim of this meeting was to provide an overview of GenoMed4All's mission, clinical pilots and relevant AI use case applications to representatives of major patients' associations in Europe covering the three diseases objective of study in this project. Speakers presented the cutting-edge advances in AI for the diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of those rare hematological (RH) domains, underlining the growing role of AI in improving and accelerating patient access to personalized medicine. At the end of presentations, an open discussion followed, in order to gather feedback from patients' representatives and discuss their issues, needs and expectations, in view of increasingly involving patients' advocates in the development of clinical AI tools.

AGENDA

6:00 PM CET WELCOME & OPENING

Welcome by GenoMed4All's Project Coordinator
Federico Álvarez, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

6:10 PM CET INTRODUCTION OF EU PATIENT ORGANIZATIONS & EU PATIENT GROUPS REPRESENTATIVES (ePAGS)

ERN-EuroBloodNet Red blood cell ePAGs
Loris Brunetta, Thalassemia International Federation

ERN-EuroBloodNet Lymphoid ePAGs
Ananda Plate, Myeloma Patients Europe

ERN-EuroBloodNet Myeloid ePAGs
Sophie Wintrich, MDS Alliance

EURORDIS
Ariane Weinman

6:30 PM CET THE GENOMED4ALL PILOTS: DISEASE OVERVIEW & CLINICAL OPEN ISSUES

Myelodysplastic Syndromes
Matteo Della Porta, Humanitas Research Hospital

Multiple Myeloma
Elena Zamagni, Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna

Sickle Cell Disease
Raffaella Colombatti, Università degli Studi di Padova

6:45 PM CET AI FOR GENOMICS & PERSONALIZED MEDICINE: CLINICAL USE CASES

AI advances in diagnosis, treatment and follow-up
Gastone Castellani, Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna

7:00 PM CET Q&A SESSION

Open audience Q&A

 GENOMED4ALL receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101017549

Figure 1. Leaflet for GenoMed4All's Patient Engagement e-Workshop (available [here](#))

Additionally, GenoMed4All training program will be aligned with the ERN-EuroBloodNet and [ENROL](#) Educational programmes in rare hematological diseases (RHDs) for health professionals and patients and the [EJP RD](#) and/or European infrastructures for research on rare diseases (RDs) to establish cross links between different sources of educational materials while avoiding overlapping.

2.3 Structure of the programme

The GenoMed4All online training programme comprises two different editions; 1st edition in 2023 – one course, 2nd edition in 2024 – two courses.

The first course, scheduled to be launched in 2023, will target a wide audience and will cover all five main areas (see [Section 2.4](#)). The overall objective of this first course is to **increase awareness**, for this purpose, each session will be focused on one specific area, including an introduction, an overview of the state of the art and the challenges in RHD.

In 2024, two additional courses will be developed, focusing on the project's onboarding strategy and showcasing tangible results and further insights about the future exploitation and long-term sustainability of GenoMed4All while exploring its relation to the private sector. Both will share the same objective, **educating and training** our audiences on the main areas of the project, but will differ on the level of the content and breadth of content. One will be adapted to a general audience while the second one will be fine-tuned for an expert audience, including any type of target group e.g. health professionals, IT experts, patients' advocates (see [Section 2.5.3.1](#)).

The following five main areas will be addressed throughout the 3 courses:

2.3.1 Introduction to GenoMed4All

2.3.1.1 The project

General overview on Genomed4all Project, EU context and added value, challenges, aims, main contributors and links with other EU initiatives e.g. [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), [Harmony Alliance](#), [Beyond 1 Million Genomes \(B1MG\)](#), [ENROL](#), [European Health Data Space \(EHDS\)](#).

2.3.1.2 Artificial Intelligence (AI) and its applications in biomedicine

The goal is to encourage as broad a group of people as possible to learn what AI is, what can and can't be done with AI in the context of biomedical applications. At the end of the webinar, we expect that people will become more confident with the concepts related to AI applications and to interpret what a prediction model implemented by an AI algorithm is able to provide and which clinical outcomes can be addressed by an AI-based method. Specifically, the following sections will be addressed:

- ❑ **AI definition:** the audience will become familiar with the concept of AI by looking into its definition and some examples. This first step is fundamental since we expect a heterogeneous audience.
- ❑ **AI problem solving approach:** the audience will be introduced in the types of general questions which the AI-based methods want to address in order to formulate a specific task with the language used by the AI algorithms.
- ❑ **AI applications in medicine:** in this section AI-based application examples will show how to shift from a classical approach of clinical decision support system (CDSS) and next generation CDSSs: Most current CDSS are mainly based on rules-based expert systems, which are designed to replicate the medication selection or recommendations derived from clinical best practices and based on the input of basic data about patient, symptoms, side effects and costs. The audience will become familiar with newly designed CDSSs where a machine-learning computer software is trained to recognize or classify specific patterns characterizing a patient or a subgroup of patients.
- ❑ **Use of multi omics (Genomics, Metabolomics, Proteomics, Radiomics) in clinical research to improve care practices:** this section will introduce the importance of considering “-omics” data in clinical research and their fundamental role to establish a precision-medicine

approach in the clinical practice. Multi-omics profiling studies enable a more comprehensive understanding of molecular changes contributing to normal development, cellular response, and disease. Using integrative omics technologies, researchers can better connect genotype to phenotype and fuel the discovery of novel drug targets and biomarkers. At the end of this section, the audience will be able to recognize the main features characterizing each type of “-omics” data and how to include these data into a clinical analysis workflow.

- **AI and multi-modal approaches for diagnosis, early risk assessment and disease progression prediction:** this last section will introduce the audience to a final example of application of machine and deep learning approaches to predict a patient outcome (e.g. disease complications, relapse) considering also the time associated to the outcome, therefore providing a tool able to predict the disease progression that can be used by the clinician as a next-generation CDSS to decide future therapies for the patient. In particular, the example will use an heterogeneous dataset including different types of information available from medical studies (e.g. clinical-, multi-omics-, imaging-based features), therefore showing the development of a multi-modal approach, which will become essential for the clinical practice in order to address a personalized medicine in the future.

2.3.2 Secure data science

2.3.2.1 Data protection

Understanding the requirements and expectations around data protection and compliance is vital. The Consortium will provide sessions on exploring the implications of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for omics and AI research in RDs. They will consider this in light of wider research governance factors, including ethics, consider the key instruments around compliance, including Data Protection Impact Assessments, Sharing Agreements and Codes of Conduct, and the implications for working in large consortia.

Additionally, the sessions will look at recently enacted and forthcoming legislation, including the Data Governance Act, European Health Data Space and AI Regulation.

2.3.2.2 How to make sensitive data discoverable

One of the main bottlenecks in human data research is the lack of tools for the secure and federated data discovery of such data. Identifiable human data requires tight privacy controls, especially now with the expansion of genomics data in clinical application, such as for medical diagnostic or prognostic purposes in RDs or cancer. Also, AI based diagnostic predictions are intrinsically tied to human biases due to lack of heterogeneity in medical data research. Medical data for AI training purposes is often characterized as mostly white and mostly male and in a

recent study, it was found that 44% of cases of liver disease among women are missed to be diagnosed¹.

Furthermore, most of the molecular analyses generated in hospitals are still stored in PDFs, locked internally, never to be utilized for further research due to the lack of proper tools for interoperable and ethical data sharing and discovery. [The Beacon project](#) (funded by [ELIXIR](#), and the [Global Alliance in Health and Genomics](#)) was created to alleviate the problem of medical genomics data discovery by enabling the discovery of genomic variants, clinical data, and other associated phenoclinic information without jeopardizing the privacy of the dataset (Figure 2). This way, any hospital or research entity can choose to 'beaconise' their dataset without compromising its privacy or ownership.

Figure 2. Overview of the Beacon project

The goal is to provide information and training about the Beacon project through the following webinars training programme (Figure 3):

- ❑ Introduction and working principles of Beacon, oriented towards clinicians & researchers working with human data and,
- ❑ Implementation or deployment of Beacon, oriented towards software developers & bioinformaticians.

¹ Straw I, Wu H. Investigating for bias in healthcare algorithms: A sex-stratified analysis of supervised machine learning models in liver disease prediction. *BMJ Heal Care Informatics*. 2022;29(1):1–8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjhci-2021-100457>

Figure 3. Training program for the Beacon project. (i) Introduction to Beacon version 1 and version 2, (ii) Beacon v2 Model, (iii) Beacon v2 Network and how to 'beaconise' clinical data.

Both sessions will be open to any audience.

- ❑ **Introduction to Beacon: Secure sharing of clinical genomics & clinical data through Beacons.** Bottlenecks of sensitive data sharing and data re-usability challenges, Patient's journey, stories, use-cases, and introduction to the Beacon pilot project launched to connect hospitals of Cataluña.
 - Introduction to **Beacon – Model** (biosamples, analysis, run, individuals, genomic annotations, cohorts, datasets).
 - Mapping of metadata and phenoclinic data on Beacon models.
 - Preparation of metadata & genomic data (VCF files) for webinar 2.
- ❑ **Demo Beacon Implementation.** Participants will learn how to make their sensitive data discoverable without jeopardizing the privacy of such a dataset through demo/hands-on training on Beacon tool reference implementation (documentation [here](#)). It is oriented towards programmers/bioinformaticians, and some command line knowledge is required.
 - Introduction to **Beacon – Framework and RI (Reference implementation)**
 - Introduction to **Beacon – API**
 - Hands-on session to install and deploy Beacon.
 - Test Beacon queries.

2.3.3 Federated Learning, equity, autonomy and reliability and regulatory requirements (including AI Regulation and EHDS directions of travel)

Federated Learning (FL) is the latest piece in the ever-growing puzzle of machine data concepts and the underlying patterns that bind them together. Thus, a fundamental step in the evolution of how we look at and understand data. The goal is to provide information and training about the federated learning concept through the following webinars:

❑ **General presentation: concept, objectives & challenges**

FL systems will be positioned in the continuum of machine data evolution.

- This evolution will be detailed through 3 dimensions: Technology/Research/Business.
- The FL concept a result from the combination of different factors.

The concept of FL will be developed. Therefore, how this works & what are the dataflows will be explained. Next, why federated learning is an attractive concept for healthcare informatics will be presented. Finally, the challenges of FL will be presented from 4 different angles:

- Business.
- Data integration.
- Security.
- Platform.

❑ **The usage of FL in GenoMed4All**

First, we will present in which context GenoMed4All has engaged with an FL approach. Then, the initial choice of the platform and the planned implementation will be detailed. Then, the challenges that the consortium is facing and what has been left aside for the current project will be presented. Finally, we describe the solution target by GenoMed4All.

2.3.4 Data standardization and interoperability in rare hematological diseases

2.3.4.1 The role of ENROL in data standardization

The objective is to present the European strategy for patients' registries in RDs and, specifically, in RHD:

- ❑ Presentation of the EU-RD-Platform, European Directory of Registries ([ERDRI.dor](#)), Central Metadata Repository ([ERDRI.mdr](#)), Pseudonymization Tool ([ERDRI.spider](#)), Search broker ([ERDRI.sebro](#)).
- ❑ Set of common data elements in RDs and domain- specific data elements – ERICA Consortium.
- ❑ The landscape of European patients' registries in RHD, the ENROL platform and its disease-specific sub-registries.
- ❑ Why we need to standardize data and how to do it? The challenge of unstructured data in the EHRs.

2.3.4.2 Common Data Model

Introduction to data model definition and data standardization into a common data model. Data models are abstract representations of the structure of the data, rather than of the data itself, designed to explicitly convey and formalize the organization of the data and the relationships among data elements, ideally achieved via the specifications of a machine-readable, codified format. Data standardization into a common format allows sharing data at the EU level through sophisticated tools for large scale research and analytics.

- ❑ Why do we need common data models?
- ❑ **Common data models in healthcare:** Some of the most notable examples include the i2b2 data model², OMOP³, PCORnet⁴, The Generalized Data Model⁵, the [FHIR interoperability standard](#)⁶.
- ❑ **Standardized terminologies and ontologies** for healthcare and clinical data are crucial to achieve consistency, by ensuring that the same coded term is used in the whole dataset to refer to the same concept or entity. Codes need to be complemented with a data dictionary to achieve semantic standardization, i.e. ensuring that all users define each entity in the same way. In addition to global terminologies as [SNOMED-CT](#), [LOINC](#), [ICD codes](#), [HPO](#), [ATC](#), [CPT](#) – we consider also other ontologies of particular relevance to RDs such as [Orphanet's ORDO](#), and [SCDO](#), as well as ontologies relevant for the genomics domain such as [HGNC](#), and [Ensembl stable IDs](#).

2.3.5 Use cases

The objective is to understand what are the challenges in HDs and specially in RHDs and how AI based solutions and GenoMed4ALL will address these challenges.

2.3.5.1 Introduction to disease areas: challenges

RHDs involve a large group of up to 450 disorders resulting from quantitative or qualitative abnormalities of blood cells, lymphoid organs and coagulation factors. Most of them are rare disorders. Nevertheless, the overall number of patients affected with a HD is important. For example, hematological malignancies account for about 5% of cancers. In addition, most HDs can cause chronic health problems and many of them are life-threatening conditions requiring

² Klann, Jeffrey G., et al. Data interchange using i2b2. Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association. 2016 ;23.5:909-915. <https://doi.org/10.1093%2Fjamia%2Focv188>

³ Overhage JM, Ryan PB, Reich CG, Hartzema AG, Stang PE. Validation of a common data model for active safety surveillance research. J Am Med Inform Assoc. 2012;19:54–60. <https://doi.org/10.1136%2Famiajnl-2011-000376>

⁴ Fleurence, Rachael L., et al. Launching PCORnet, a national patient-centered clinical research network. Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association. 2014;21.4:578-582. <https://doi.org/10.1136%2Famiajnl-2014-002747>

⁵ Danese, Mark D., et al. The generalized data model for clinical research. BMC medical informatics and decision making 19.1 (2019):1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-019-0837-5>

⁶ Bender, Duane, and Kamran Sartipi. HL7 FHIR: An Agile and RESTful approach to healthcare information exchange. Proceedings of the 26th IEEE international symposium on computer-based medical systems. IEEE, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CBMS.2013.6627810>

numerous resources and multidisciplinary teams for their correct diagnosis, management and treatment, representing a public health challenge.

GenoMed4All aims to demonstrate the potential and benefits of trustable and explainable AI technologies, with a novel approach to AI models and algorithms to exploit the powerful set of “omics” data which will be at researchers’ disposal leading to more reliable and meaningful outcomes for advancing research and personalized medicine, with three use cases covering oncological and non-oncological HDs.

The majority of hematologic disorders both inherited or acquired have a genetic background and the use cases we have selected for our purposes are different from each other.

- ❑ **Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS)** is an oncological acquired disease that displays acquired somatic mutations. The challenge in MDS is to explain the extreme genomic heterogeneity in terms of mutations and mutation interactions.
- ❑ **Sickle Cell Disease (SCD)** is a non-oncological and congenital disease displaying inherited mutations within the same gene. The challenge for this disease is to find clinical, genomic, metabolomics and rheology determinants in the context of a monogenic disease.
- ❑ **Multiple Myeloma (MM)** is an oncological acquired disease which displays somatic genomic alterations. This disease involves the bone marrow and some other solid organs, including the bone that can be studied through radiomics technique. The challenge for MM is to put into correlation radiomics and genomics by exploiting AI algorithms.

2.3.5.2 Myelodysplastic Syndromes use case

The goal is to provide an overview of the main challenges of MDS and how to use AI/contribute with your datasets: How to approach genomics in MDS. Comprehensive analyses on a large patient population with clinical and “omics” data (e.g., DNA-sequencing and RNA-sequencing) are warranted to:

- ❑ Presentation of the [EU-RD-Platform](#), European Directory of Registries ([ERDRI.dor](#)), Central Metadata Repository ([ERDRI.mdr](#)), Pseudonymization Tool ([ERDRI.spider](#)), Search broker ([ERDRI.sebro](#)).
- ❑ Investigate -omics factors that influence the development of MDS and enable early identification of individuals at risk.
- ❑ Define innovative prognostic models and effective methods to predict: overall survival/risk of leukemic evolution and the individual probability of disease relapse after HSCT.
- ❑ Improve the classification of the disease.
- ❑ Better stratify the individual probability of response to specific treatments.
- ❑ Provide a rationale of drugs repurposing for specific subsets of MDS.

According to the scope of the training and educational activities, MDS partners identified possible topics to be addressed during the webinars scheduled for 2023 and 2024:

- ❑ The relevance of MDS-registries to accelerate translational and clinical research (including an introductory session).
- ❑ AI-based decision support systems for myelodysplastic syndromes.
- ❑ Application of AI to define innovative biomarkers in MDS.
- ❑ Personalized medicine in MDS: Artificial intelligence to improve diagnosis and prognosis.

2.3.5.3 Sickle Cell Disease use case

The goal is to provide an overview of the main challenges of SCD and how to use AI/contribute with your datasets: How to approach multi-omics in SCD.

SCD is a monogenic disease with a wide clinical spectrum. The variables determining a specific clinical behavior are still unknown hampering patients' risk classification to develop acute and chronic complications of the disease, e.g., chronic organ damage is invisible to clinician's eye before it is already established. Choice of treatment is based on clinical experience and studies with short number of patients.

Bone marrow transplant is currently the only curative treatment option but high risks. Many new drugs are on clinical trials and will come into the market very soon. What patients will benefit the most from each treatment option (according to their predicted severity)?

Development of AI-based scores to predict the risk and time of occurrence of severe complications (Vaso occlusive crisis, Stroke (hemorrhagic and ischemic), Renal impairment, Hepatic failure, Silent infarcts, Retinopathy) combining clinical and laboratory data, functional test data (ektacitometry), genetic modifiers information (GWAS) and metabolomics.

Development of AI algorithms that can analyze the MRI of patients to be able to detect silent infarcts or precursor lesions.

According to the scope of the training and educational activities, SCD partners identified possible topics to be addressed during the webinars scheduled for 2023 and 2024:

- ❑ SCD Introduction to disease and research challenges.
- ❑ Objectives and how to use AI / contribute with your datasets.
- ❑ Genomics in SCD.
- ❑ Metabolomics in SCD.
- ❑ Rheology in SCD.
- ❑ Radiomics in SCD: Identification of WMHR (White Matter Hyperintense Regions) in MRI brain scan with AI.
- ❑ Personalized Medicine in SCD.

2.3.5.4 Multiple Myeloma use case

The goal is to provide an overview of the main challenges of MM and how to use AI/contribute with your datasets: How to approach genomics and radiomics in MM.

MM is a plasma cell neoplasm characterized by the proliferation of monoclonal plasma cells, mainly in the bone marrow. MM is a heterogeneous disease with more than 25% of patients at diagnosis presenting with high-risk features.

There is a clear gap in addressing the role both of multi-modal imaging and of liquid biopsy data, regarding patient outcome prediction as well as their correlations and interplay with genetic factors that can pave the way to personalized treatment in MM.

The successful treatment of MM is hampered by the genetic heterogeneity of the disease since different genetic characteristics can result in different responses to treatment.

Comprehensive analyses on a large patient population with clinical and “omics” data (e.g. DNA-sequencing and RNA-sequencing) are warranted to:

- ❑ **Describe the MM complexity:** to describe the different layers of MM heterogeneity, by integrating baseline genomic and imaging data to better define clonal and spatial heterogeneity of MM patients at baseline. Genomic data will be obtained both from BM clone and from liquid biopsy.
- ❑ **Describe the MM evolution dynamics:** to define the quantitative and qualitative dynamics of the disease in time, by molecularly quantifying the minimal residual disease and by describing its distribution with both different imaging techniques (PET-CT and MRI) and liquid biopsy data at pre-defined time-points.
- ❑ **Define the risk of MM progression:** to develop AI-based a prognostic risk score including clinical, genomic and imaging data describing both the baseline disease and the disease remaining after therapy.
- ❑ **Radiomics and radiogenomics model development and prospective validation:** (a) to predict treatment response based on multi-modal radiomics (WBMRI, PET/CT); (b) to investigate the sensitivity and specificity of both WB-MRI and PET-CT imaging techniques in detecting residual disease; (c) to determine progression-free survival (PFS).

According to the scope of the training and educational activities, MM partners identified possible topics to be addressed during the webinars scheduled for 2023 and 2024:

- ❑ Personalized Medicine in SCD.
- ❑ Introduction to Multiple Myeloma: genomic landscape of the disease and radiomics.
- ❑ How to approach genomics and radiomics in Multiple myeloma in the refinement of risk stratification.
- ❑ Application of AI in the upfront identification of early-relapse patients.
- ❑ Added value of AI in Multiple Myeloma as compared to current approaches.
- ❑ Contribute with our datasets: cohort description.
- ❑ Data integration in MM, AI and Machine Learning (ML) approaches.

2.4 Courses and Webinars definition

The Genomed4All webinar programme will be delivered in two waves:

- ❑ **First wave 2023:**
 - First course: What is GenoMed4All and the core areas covered.
- ❑ **Second wave 2024:**
 - First course: Onboarding strategy for our general audience.
 - Second course: Onboarding strategy for our expert audience.

The GenoMed4All webinar training programme will follow the design and strategy of the Topic on Focus ERN-EuroBloodNet educational programme and will be organized in all logistical aspects by ERN-EuroBloodNet and in collaboration with **GenoMed4All ES/TC** (see [Section 2.1](#)). The Topic on Focus ERN-EuroBloodNet program is dedicated to increase awareness and educate & train RHDs target groups. Until now, ERN-EuroBloodNet has organized:

- ❑ **3 Topic on Focus for Health professionals** (targeting the last advances on cutaneous lymphoma, thrombotic microangiopathies and bone marrow failure syndromes),
- ❑ **3 Topic on Focus for Patients and their families** (on myelodysplastic syndromes, sickle cell disease and splastic anemia and paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria).
- ❑ **1 Topic on Focus for Patients Organizations** (dedicated to cutaneous lymphoma).

As the ERN-EuroBloodNet programmes, training dedicated to Health professionals will be accredited by [the European Board for Accreditation in Hematology \(EBAH\)](#).

Specifically, for what concerns **logistics and webinar structure**: each webinar session will be conducted on a Learning Management Platform, such as Zoom. Thanks to this format the communication between speakers and audience will be possible. Sessions will rely on the visual aid of a PowerPoint presentation and will be recorded.

Each online live session will have a duration of 60 min, and will consist of two parts: first, the lecture itself, and second, a Q&A Session. The lecture will be presented by the selected speaker/s during the first 45 min of the session, who will then answer the audience's doubts and questions for the last 15 minutes. The [Slido platform](#) will be used to ensure a smooth live interaction between the attendees and the speakers.

2.5 Communication and Dissemination strategy

The design and implementation of a robust communication and dissemination plan is the cornerstone to reach a critical mass, both in terms of audience numbers and level of interest, that is necessary to ensure widespread participation and meaningful engagement in GenoMed4All's training program, which directly feeds into and shapes the overall outreach strategy of the GenoMed4All project.

2.5.1 Visual identity of the programme

As a fundamental dissemination initiative within the project, GenoMed4All's training program will become part of GenoMed4All's branding. As such, all materials and multimedia contents (e.g., webinar presentation templates, video recordings, training catalogues, infographics...) will follow GenoMed4All's already established visual identity and design principles.

2.5.2 Registration and content

The [ERN-EuroBloodNet website](#), the main tool for communication and dissemination of the ERN on RHDs, will be used as the central platform for all the aspects concerning the registration of the Genomed4All training program. The website, which has received **over 170K page visits**, has implemented a specific tool for education actions that enables (Figure 4 and Figure 5):

- ❑ Registration to the session/s.
- ❑ Distribution of satisfaction questionnaires and gathering of answers.
- ❑ Repository of content for publicly available.

The screenshot displays the ERN-EuroBloodNet website interface. The main heading is 'ERN-EuroBloodNet Topic on Focus: Thrombotic Microangiopathies'. Below this, there is a detailed text block describing the program's objectives and structure. To the right, a 'Past webinars' section is visible, featuring a grid of webinar cards. Each card includes the webinar title, date, speaker, target audience, and a 'View' button. The cards shown are: 'TTP and ADAMTS13 Pathophysiology (ADAMTS13-related TTP pathophysiology)', 'Animal models of TTP', 'Diagnostic workup for TTP and TMA syndromes: pitfalls', and 'Present and future of TTP treatment'.

Figure 4. Design of the ERN-EuroBloodNet Educational Programme website section. Genomed4All's training program section will have the same appearance and structure on ERN-EuroBloodNet's website.

TTP and ADAMTS13: Pathophysiology (ADAMTS13-related TTP pathophysiology)

03/02/2022 16:00

Speakers: **Veronique Agnes**

Target: Health professionals

Subnetworks: Bleeding - Coagulation disorders

Prof. Agnès Veyradier graduated in Medicine in Paris University (France) in 1997 and she obtained her PhD in Haematology in 2000. Since 2005, she has been nominated as a professor of Haematology at Paris University School of Medicine. She is currently head of the haematology department of the hospital Group Lariboisière-Saint Louis (Assistance Publique-Hopital de Paris) and she also coordinates both the national ADAMTS13/Thrombotic Thrombocytopenic Purpura laboratory of the National Reference Center for Thrombotic Microangiopathies and the Paris site of the National Reference Center for von Willebrand disease. She is author of over 100 articles in peer-reviewed journals.

To receive the access link to the Webinar, please register here:

* Fields are required

Name*

Surname*

Age range*

Select an option

Role*

Select an option

Mail*

Healthcare Provider*

Select an option

Country*

Select an option

I have read and accept the [privacy policy](#)

SEND

Figure 5. Design of the ERN-EuroBloodNet webinar section. Each Genomed4All’s webinar will have the same appearance and structure on ERN-EuroBloodNet’s website: Registration form and information about the speaker

The [GenoMed4All website](#) (Figure 6), with **over 8.3K page visits**, will host direct links to the section dedicated to this program in the [ERN-EuroBloodNet website](#) to reroute the traffic of visitors aiming to maximize the number of registrations. At the same time, links to the [GenoMed4All website](#) will also be included in the section dedicated to this program on the [ERN-EuroBloodNet website](#) to increase the outreach of the project among [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#) stakeholders.

Figure 6. GenoMed4All's website – homepage

The educational content generated will be publicly available in the sections that will be created for this training program on both websites. **Figure 7** shows an example from an [ERN-EuroBloodNet webinar section](#).

Figure 7. Design of the ERN-EuroBloodNet webinar section. The content generated will be publicly available on the corresponding Genomed4Alls’s webinar section

2.5.3 Outreach plan for the Programme

2.5.3.1 Target groups and audience definition

The definition of GenoMed4All’s training programme target groups is essential to identify their needs, adapt the content and promote their engagement. In line with the project content, the partners involved, and the target groups defined in the **D9.1 – GenoMed4All Impact Master Plan**, the following stakeholders have been identified (**Figure 8**):

Figure 8. Key audience and target groups for GenoMed4All's training programme

To ensure their interest in the programme, the content of the courses will be shaped by taking into consideration different levels of expertise, as mentioned in [section 2.3](#). Thereby, stakeholders will be able to follow the course targeting:

- ❑ **General audience:** if they have non-existent or basic knowledge of the topics; or
- ❑ **Expert audience:** if they already have expertise.

2.5.3.2 Webinar promotion and communication

To foster engagement among the identified stakeholders in each session of the program the following channels and tools will be used by both [AUSTRALO](#) and [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), as the ones leading all promotional efforts. The main metrics and performance of the online channels of each initiative can be found in [Table 2](#). Moreover, [GenoMed4All's partners](#) will contribute to this action by distributing the information among their institutions and networks.

Available tools	GenoMed4All	ERN-EuroBloodNet
Twitter followers	917	1326
LinkedIn followers	466	490
Facebook followers	N/A	328
YouTube Channel	12	362
Website visits	1.9K visitors, 8.3K pageviews	over 170K page visits
Newsletter receivers	N/A	874*

*The [ERN-EuroBloodNet Newsletter](#) is also shared among National Scientific Societies and with the [European Hematology Association \(EHA\)](#) which has further agreed to share it within their own community.

Table 2. Communication tools in numbers

Newsletters and email campaigns will be created for the dissemination of the webinar program, including concrete details for each webinar (title, date and time), the photo and the biography/ies of the speakers, and links to the dedicated [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#) website section.

Details for connection will be sent by e-mail to each registrant including a summary of the webinar. This point will set the basis for the comprehension of the webinar and the identification of doubts in advance to be solved by the speaker during the lecture.

2.5.3.3 Dissemination of the knowledge and training contents

The strategy for disseminating the content of the program will involve several actions:

- ❑ **Video recorded webinars** will be publicly available on the [ERN-EuroBloodNet YouTube Channel](#) (Figure 9) and [GenoMed4All YouTube Channel](#) and accessible afterwards.
- ❑ Creation of a **public repository of slides and video**: The dedicated section on each website, [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#) and [GenoMed4All](#), will include the link to the video published on [YouTube](#) and the pdf document of the slides of the session.
- ❑ Creation of **training pills**: With the aim to disseminate relevant content among the community, short videos will be extracted from the webinar sessions recordings. These videos will also help to maintain the engagement of the audience during the first course in 2023 and the courses in 2024.
- ❑ Production of a **catalogue or training course** compilation based on the abstracts provided by the speakers and sent to the attendees prior to each session.

Figure 9. Example of an educational playlist of the ERN-EuroBloodNet EDU YouTube Channel

2.6 Evaluation of the training programme

Establishing a performance review is essential to evaluate the success of the program. For this purpose, the definition of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is necessary (Table 3). The Kirkpatrick Model will be explored and eventually adopted.

KPIs	Definition and methodology	Target
Number of attendees	Number of attendees per country will be analyzed. The data will be gathered through a registration form placed on the EU survey website .	40 attendees per session (min.).
Satisfaction questionnaires	Rating questions will be created to evaluate attendee's experience. The delivery of the questions and gathering of the answers will be enabled with the ERN-EuroBloodNet education tool described in Section 2.5.2 .	Minimum rating of 5 .
Number of views on YouTube	Total number of views per video will be extracted directly from the YouTube channel.	50 views per video (min.).

Table 3. Key Performance Indicators

3 Conclusions

The information contained in this deliverable comprises the **first phase of the development of the GenoMed4All training programme, which is focused on the definition of the topics and methodologies**. The second phase, focused on the development and the results, will be provided in deliverable **D8.6 Final report on the GenoMed4All training** at the end of the project.

The development of this task is the result of joint efforts from the leader (VHIR), [ERN-EuroBloodNet](#), AUSTRALO and the cooperation of the **GenoMed4All ES/TC**. The **creation** of the committee has been crucial to assess the objective of this first phase.

First, **5 main topics have been identified** according to the core areas of GenoMed4All. This selection has set the basis for the definition of the lectures that will be delivered.

Second, the training program will consist of a series of webinar courses designed to **increase awareness** and to **educate & train to different knowledge audiences**, on the different topics involved in the GenoMed4All project. For this purpose, **three courses will be carried out in 2023 and 2024**.

Third, the comprehensive webinar program of **GenoMed4All will leverage and capitalize on the central resources provided by ERN-EuroBloodNet and GenoMed4All**. The ERN has developed an e-learning environment on its website under an easily accessible platform containing a wide range of educational materials for different target groups: health professionals, patients and patients' organizations. This is a repository for classifying documents issued from educational programs, video recorded from hosted webinars and a list of the ongoing and upcoming webinar programs. Recorded video of the session will be edited and then published together with the lecture slides on each webinar's dedicated section (for [patients](#) and [health professionals](#)) and [ERN-EuroBloodNet's EDU YouTube channel](#). The educational content will be also available on the [GenoMed4All website](#) and [YouTube channel](#).

Fourth, each **60 minutes webinar** will be moderated by a member of the ERN-EuroBloodNet team, who will present the speaker and will enable the discussion during the **questions and answers session (15 minutes)** after the presentation.

Fifth, the **content generated** (videos, slides, training pills and training catalogue) will stimulate **the outreach** of the project's boost.

Finally, the **evaluation of the training programme** will be carried out based on the **KPI's achievement**.

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